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Leveraging in-situ anionic polymerization of polyamide 6 for high performance basalt- and flax-fiber thermoplastic laminates

*Giulia Cotti Comettini¹, Martino Valentini¹, Olivier De Almeida², Andrea Dorigato¹, Markus Kakkonen³,
Gerhard Kalinka⁴, Pasi Kallio⁵, Marco Papparotto¹, Alessandro Pegoretti¹, **Giulia Fredi**¹*

*¹University of Trento, Italy; ²Institut Clément Ader - IMT Mines Albi, France; ³Fibrobotics Oy, Finland; ⁴BAM Federal Institute for
Materials Research and Testing, Germany; ⁵Tampere University, Finland*

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giulia.fredi@unitn.it

Thermoplastic composites: traditional and reactive processing

Thermoplastic composites

- shorter thermal cycles → increased production rate
- «infinite» shelf life
- post-thermoformability and recyclability
- High viscosity
- High-temperature processing

- **low-viscosity** precursors
- complete fiber **impregnation**
- **shorter and less complex** production cycles

Polyamide 6 (PA6): reactive vs. melt processing

10.1016/j.compositesa.2006.05.007

PA6: hydrolytic vs. anionic polymerization

Hydrolytic polymerization

- $T = 250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($> T_c$)
- Hours-Days

- $M_w = 30\text{ kg/mol}$
- Conv. $> 90\%$
- $X_c = 20\text{-}30\%$
- $E = 2\text{-}3\text{ GPa}$

Anionic (ring-opening) polymerization

- $T = 140\text{-}170\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($< T_c$)
- Seconds-minutes

suitable for reactive processing

- $M_w = 500\text{ kg/mol}$
- Conv. $> 99\%$
- $X_c = 40\text{-}50\%$
- $E = 3\text{-}4\text{ GPa}$

extremely moisture-sensitive

Initiation

Initiation with an activator (faster)

Common initiators:

Bruggolen C10

Dilactamate

Common activator:

Bruggolen C20P

Aim of the work

Prepare and characterize aPA6-matrix composites with two types of continuous reinforcement:

1. Basalt fiber fabric

BAS220P (Basaltex NV)

- 220 g/m²
- Plain
- (3-glycidyloxypropyl)trimethoxysilane sizing
- 3 types of surface state

2. Flax fiber fabric

Flax fabric Flaxdry BL200 (Eco-Technilin)

- 200 g/m²
- Twill
- Twisted yarns
- 3 types of surface state

Outline

PA6/BF

- Monomer conversion
- Mechanical properties
- Fiber/matrix adhesion

PA6/FF

- Why plant fibers + anionic PA6?
- Fiber surface state
- Monomer conversion
- Mechanical properties

A grayscale scanning electron micrograph (SEM) showing the surface morphology of a PA6/basalt fiber composite. The image displays a complex, layered structure with numerous small, irregular particles and fibers embedded within a matrix. The overall appearance is highly textured and porous. The text "PA6/basalt fiber composites" is overlaid in the center of the image.

PA6/basalt fiber composites

Preparation of PA6/BF laminates via tRTM

Reactive in situ activated polymerization – Thermoplastic resin transfer molding

Sample	Reinforcement	Monomer conversion (%)	ϑ_v (vol%)	ϑ_f (vol%)
PA6/BFa	As-received BF	97.2	6.6	28.2
PA6/BFw	BF washed with ethanol	97.7	1.4	31.5
PA6/BFu	Thermally desized BF (400 °C – 4 h)	98.7	3.4	32.4

Valentini, ... and Fredi, Composites A 2025, 190, 108681, 10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108681

PA6/BF: microstructure

PA6/BFa and PA6/BFw:

- Matrix residues on the fibers
- Matrix deformation
- (slight) improvement with washing
→ good fiber/matrix adhesion

PA6/BFu:

- Clean fibers and grooves
→ scarce fiber/matrix adhesion

Valentini,... and Fredi, Composites A 2025, 190, 108681, [10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108681](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108681)

3-point bending test

- Ethanol washing significantly increases the stiffness and strength
- Desizing decreases the mechanical properties
- TT at 400 °C may decrease the BF strength but not the stiffness
- Theoretical stiffness (mixture rule):
 - PA6/BFa: 13.0 GPa
 - PA6/BFw: 14.2 GPa
 - PA6/BFu: 14.5 GPa

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Interfacial adhesion: three tests

Short beam shear (SBS) test

$$ILSS = F^{SBS} = \frac{3P_m}{4bh}$$

- 3-p bending with a short specimen
- Maximization of shear stresses
- Delamination promoted

Single fiber push out (SFPO) test

$$IFSS = F^{SFPO} = \frac{P_m}{2\pi r_f l_f}$$

- Thin (tens of μm) specimen
- Fiber is pushed out of the matrix

Microbond (MD) test

$$IFSS = F^{MD} = \frac{P_m}{2\pi r_f l_f}$$

- Droplets of matrix on the fiber
- Fiber is drawn out of the droplet

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Interfacial adhesion

Short beam vs push out:

- Dispersion is higher with a micro-scale test but trends are similar:
 - PA6/BFw: washing increases adhesion
 - PA6/BFu: desizing decreases adhesion

Microdebonding:

- Lower adhesion

- Ductile droplets:** residual monomer
- Porous droplets:** overestimation of the interfacial area

Valentini, ... and Fredi, Composites A 2025, 190, 108681, 10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108681

PA6/BF: conclusions

- **Fiber surface treatment critically determines fiber-matrix adhesion** (simple treatment effective with a sensitive polymerization reaction), **while the bulk matrix properties are not affected**
- **Ethanol washing** emerged as the most effective treatment, increasing short-beam shear strength by 14% compared to as-received fibers (51.9 ± 8.2 MPa vs 45.5 ± 3.2 MPa)
- Thermal desizing at 400°C significantly impaired interfacial bonding, reducing interfacial shear strength by ~50% (19.6 ± 1.2 MPa)
- **Multi-technique characterization** (short-beam shear, fiber push-out, microdebonding) provided complementary insights into interfacial behavior at different scales, but **the microdebonding test presents challenges that are unique of this matrix system**

aPA6/flax fiber composites

Lignocellulosic reinforcements: industrial applications

Key Benefits (vs. glass)

- High specific properties
- Cost-effective production
- Bio-based
- Biodegradable
- Other functional properties (e.g., vibration-damping)

Automotive Industry

- Hemp, jute, flax, sisal fibers
- Seat cushions, interior panels, front grills

Transportation

- Aircraft interior components
- Boat hulls
- Pressure vessels (w/ thermosetting resins)

Construction & Building

- Wood-plastic composites for furniture & decking
- Hemp/lime concrete for soundproofing
- Recycled WPC in asphalt & concrete

Consumer & Sports Goods

- Musical instruments
- Sport equipment
- Packaging

Lignocellulosic reinforcements in polymers: three main challenges

Challenge 1: Poor interfaces

Poor interfacial interaction with polymer matrices, for two main reasons:

- 1) **Hygroscopicity** and swelling (enhanced by fiber porosity)
- 2) **Hydrophilicity** and poor chemical compatibility with hydrophobic polymer matrices

Challenge 2: Poor stability

Poor thermal and environmental stability, so:

- 1) **Degradation during processing ($T > 200^{\circ}\text{C}$):** challenges with technical thermoplastics
- 2) **Degradation during use:** attack by microorganisms and fungi; flammability

Challenge 3: Property variability

Variability and challenges in measuring mechanical properties:

- 1) **Variable morphology** and irregular cross section
- 2) **Variability due to environmental conditions**

Bonus challenge

Decreased **durability** of durable composites (and of the biodegradable ones?)

Lignocellulosic reinforcements in polymers: poor thermal stability

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2024.04.085>

Degradation during processing ($T > 200^{\circ}\text{C}$)

- restricts manufacturing temperature
- limits the matrix selection to:

Thermosets
with curing temp.
below 200°C

**Low-melting-temperature
thermoplastics**
e.g., PE, PP, PLA

- Unfair competition with glass fibers
- Restricts broader industrial applications:
challenges with technical thermoplastics like PET, PA, PEEK, etc.

Weight loss (%)	T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 5wt%	T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 25wt%	T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 50wt%	T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 75wt%
Hemp	105	329	341	458
Kenaf	64	313	341	371
Henequen	61	301	337	392
Flax	88	323	339	441
Glass	586	-	-	-

PA6/flax: aim of the work

Produce and characterize

polymer composites combining

lignocellulosic fibers and an

engineering polymer matrix (polyamide 6) exploiting

in situ reactive processing, which allows low precursor's viscosity and low processing temperatures

- Activated anionic ring-opening polymerization
- **Extremely sensitive to moisture and surface impurities** (initiator reacts with proton donating species and deactivates \rightarrow lower degree of conversion)

Flax fabric Flaxdry BL200

Three surface states:

- **NT**: not treated (as received)
- **A**: silanized with APTES (spray coated)
- **HA**: treated with hexane, ethanol, acetone (HEA) and then silanized with APTES

Increase degree of conversion and interfacial adhesion

Characterization of the fibers: microstructure

- Decrease in twist angle with both treatments
- No clear effects on the surface morphology

Twist angle (Orientation J – ImageJ)

Characterization of the fibers: silanization

Characterization of the fibers: silanization

- Successful silanization
- Silanization seems more effective if preceded by HEA treatment

Characterization of the fibers: tensile tests

Tensile tests

- Single fibers
- Yarns →

- HA treatment **decreases the strain at break and the break tenacity**, but not the max load → increase in linear density

	Yarn (tex)	Staple (tex)
NT	107 ± 27	0.3483 ± 0.0007
A	115 ± 24	0.4248 ± 0.0007
HA	120 ± 34	0.4509 ± 0.0007

- the decrease is significant (for HA) but slight
- The **stiffness [N/tex]** is not significantly affected

One-way ANOVA and Tukey's HSD test at $p = 0.05$

Preparation of PA6/flax laminates via tRTM

Reactive in situ activated polymerization – Thermoplastic resin transfer molding

reactive mixture:

- ϵ -CL
- initiator (Dilactamate)
- activator (C20P)

initiator
(4.38 phr)

activator
(1.49 phr)

- Moisture-tolerant initiator (other initiators like NaCl perform worse)

PA6/flax composites: monomer conversion

DSC (first heating scan)

TGA

- aPA6 melting point decreases more with NT flax and less with A and HA flax
- Same trend for the conversion degree

Degree of conversion (%)

aPA6	97.6
aPA6/NT	89.5
aPA6/A	93.9
aPA6/HA	95.1

Better than literature data
(DL is an effective initiator)

PA6/flax composites: tensile tests

Unreinforced aPA6

E (GPa)	2.8 ± 0.3
UTS (MPa)	60 ± 1
Strain at break (%)	63 ± 19

Tensile fracture surface

Matrix impregnation and packing factor (μ)

μ , convex hull method

0.62 ± 0.07

0.54 ± 0.05

0.64 ± 0.10

μ , concentric circles method

0.52 ± 0.08

0.42 ± 0.06

0.45 ± 0.07

Conclusions

- APTES silanization, especially if preceded by solvent treatment, **increases the monomer conversion, matrix penetration, interfacial adhesion and mechanical properties**
- The chosen initiator (Dilactamate) is suitable to reach **a high (89-95 %) degree of conversion** with a challenging reinforcement (moisture sensitivity of the anionic polymerization)
- The process and the surface treatment **has been proven effective** with a type of flax reinforcement (bidirectional highly twisted)

Current and future work

- Test the **impact** and **short-beam shear (SBS)** properties on the composites
- Explore **more environmentally sustainable surface treatments** (e.g., enzymatic treatment, collab. Univ. Ferrara, Italy)
- Look for **property maximization** with non-twisted UD fibers

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Giulia Fredi

Junior assistant professor, University of Trento (Italy)

Fulbright visiting scholar (2025), MIT AeroAstro (USA)

✉ giulia.fredi@unitn.it

 <https://www.linkedin.com/in/giulia-fredi/>

 <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=nKeRFU0AAAAJ&hl=it&oi=ao>

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Tensile tests on neat PA6

Instron 5969; ISO 527 1BA specimens; 10 mm/min.

- trends of E follow the crystallinity; high ductility at intermediate temperatures
- 165-L: good compromise → **matrix for BF laminates**

Fredi et al, Polymer 2024, 311, 127562. 10.1016/j.polymer.2024.127562